

CCSDS 123.0-B-2 Compression Standard Cross-validation and Fuzzing

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“The use of standards is growing, the importance of standardisation for the competitiveness and public good is undisputed, but the general awareness and training on standardisation is comparably small. There is no formal education nor vocational training on standardisation. [...]”

CCSDS 123.0-B-2 Recommended Standard for Low-Complexity Lossless and Near-Lossless Multispectral and Hyperspectral Image Compression

'Cross-validation'

* Same 'cross-validation' approach applied in CCSDS 123.0-B-2 (2019), CCSDS 121.0-B-3 (2020), CCSDS 124.0-B-1 (upcoming).

Four Participants

Problem:

- could not share source code nor executable files, and
- configuration space for '123' is very large.

☞ We used fuzzing to produce tests vectors!

Outline

- 1 Fuzzing “Boot Camp”
- 2 How we fuzzed CCSDS-123.0-B-2
- 3 Results

Fuzzing "Boot Camp"

Coverage-guided Fuzzing

```
long factorial(int n)
{
  int c;
  long result = 1;
  for (c = 1; c <= n; c++)
    result = result * c;
  return result;
}
```

A coverage graph for the original code, showing a single path that starts at the beginning of the function, goes down to the for loop, then up to the return statement, and finally down to the end of the function.

Original code (path) coverage

```
long factorial(int n)
{
  int c;
  long result = 1;
  for (c = 1; c <= n; c++)
    result = result * c;
  return result;
}
```

A coverage graph for the discarded code, showing a path that starts at the beginning of the function, goes down to the for loop, then up to the return statement, and finally down to the end of the function. This path is identical to the original code's path.

Same coverage: discard

```
long factorial(int n)
{
  int c;
  long result = 1;
  for (c = 1; c <= n; c++)
    result = result * c;
  return result;
}
```

A coverage graph for the new code, showing a path that starts at the beginning of the function, goes down to the for loop, then up to the return statement, and finally down to the end of the function. This path is identical to the original code's path.

New coverage: add to test set

Fuzzing Harness

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Our Setup

Fuzzer: American Fuzzy Lop (AFL)

```
american fuzzy lop 0.47b (readpng)

process timing
  run time      : 0 days, 0 hrs, 4 min, 43 sec
  last new path : 0 days, 0 hrs, 0 min, 26 sec
  last uniq crash : none seen yet
  last uniq hang : 0 days, 0 hrs, 1 min, 51 sec
cycle progress
  now processing : 38 (19.49%)
  paths timed out : 0 (0.00%)
stage progress
  now trying : interest 32/8
  stage execs : 0/9990 (0.00%)
  total execs : 654k
  exec speed : 2306/sec
fuzzing strategy yields
  bit flips : 88/14.4k, 6/14.4k, 6/14.4k
  byte flips : 0/1804, 0/1786, 1/1750
  arithmetics : 31/126k, 3/45.6k, 1/17.8k
  known ints : 1/15.8k, 4/65.8k, 6/78.2k
  havoc : 34/254k, 0/0
  trim : 2876 B/931 (61.45% gain)

overall results
  cycles done : 0
  total paths : 195
  uniq crashes : 0
  uniq hangs : 1
map coverage
  map density : 1217 (7.43%)
  count coverage : 2.55 bits/tuple
findings in depth
  favored paths : 128 (65.64%)
  new edges on : 85 (43.59%)
  total crashes : 0 (0 unique)
  total hangs : 1 (1 unique)
path geometry
  levels : 3
  pending : 178
  pend fav : 114
  imported : 0
  variable : 0
  latent : 0
```

Hardware: A single Threadripper 1950X (32 threads) with overclocked 3200 Mhz DDR4 RAM.

- ☞ AFL needs an ad-hoc multi-node setup, which we did not have time to develop for our cluster.
- ☞ Ran fast (300k execs/sec), and very hot.

Crossvalidation Harness

Basic Idea:

- 1- Read data from STDIN
- 2- Decode with 123.0-B-2
- 3- Rencode with 123.0-B-2
- 4- Compare data from STDIN with reencoded data.
- 5- Crash program if it does not match.

Software

UAB's implementation was coded with fuzz testing in mind:

- | | | |
|----------------------------------|---|---|
| Code is full of assertions | → | Harness crashes if inconsistencies are detected. |
| No undefined behavior | → | We can fuzz with UBSan (crash on undefined behavior; this includes signed integer overflows). |
| No default memory initialization | → | We can detect uninitialized memory accesses (valgrind or MSan). |

Crossvalidation Harness

Basic Idea:

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Issues

- ☞ Should an invalid sample crash the harness?
- ☞ What happens when we get a 123.0-B-2 that we can decode but is not a valid 123.0-B-2 file?
Block-adaptive encoder, I'm looking at you!
- ☞ Previous harness does not test optional tables.
How can we test optional tables if the fuzzer only generates one file?
- ☞ How do we test Supplementary Information Tables (SITs)?

The Actual Crossvalidation Harness

(left side)

(right side)

The Actual Crossvalidation Harness (left side)

👉 Invalid input files stop the decoder.

The Actual Crossvalidation Harness (left side)

This may not match!

- Some files can be decoded, but no encoder would ever produce them, and
- We are switching the 'optionality' of optional tables.

The Actual Crossvalidation Harness (right side)

👉 Invalid input files **crash** the decoder.

The Actual Crossvalidation Harness

— Comparisons

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Test Sets

Test Set 1: fuzzing samples that decode successfully.

- 15 million+ executions
- 7946 synthetic images
- 1.5 MBytes

Test Set 2: settings from Test Set 1 × raw images from CCSDS MHDC corpus.

- 17401 test cases
- 902 GBytes input, 2.1 TBytes output
- Only checksums

Test Set 3: samples that do not decode properly.

- Not necessary for crossvalidation
- 10368 test cases
- Painful to pass

Other 'hand-crafted' test patterns: hybrid encoder codewords, high dynamic range, ...

Outcomes and Lessons Learned

Cross-validation achieved after $\simeq 150$ e-mails, $\simeq 5$ test vector iterations, and **many** bugs detected!

- ☞ If a software has not been fuzzed, it **will** likely contain errors.
- ☞ When you start to see the end, you are half-way.
- ☞ Use a header to configure a compressor.
- ☞ Save unit testing for corner cases not covered by fuzzing.
- ☞ Low coverage for non-feature-complete implementations.

From the (proud) **authors of...**

The
unofficial,

not that accurate,

but hopefully very informative

description of CCSDS-123.0-B-2

**OBPDC
2018**

OBPDC 2022

**A fuzzing harness that does not
produce test vectors but is really cool**

Test Input

Harness

Tested program

Harness

Test Input

Test Input

Harness

Tested program

Test Input

Harness

Tested program

What should the music score be?

./lcnl_encoder f000 u8be f001 f002

“Score”	Description
0x02,	Tool is ‘lcnl_encoder’.
0x01,	FILE; push file name to argument list.
0x00, 0x75, 0x38, 0x62, 0x65, 0x00,	ARGUMENT; push string ‘u8be’ to the argument list.
0x01,	FILE; push file name to argument list.
0x01,	FILE; push file name to argument list.
0x6e,	Unknown action; end of argument list construction.
0x02, 0x00, 0x00, 0x00, 0x00, 0x02, ..., 0x01, 0x00,	Contents of the first file are 0x00, 0x00, 0x02, ..., 0x01.
0x05, 0x85, 0x85, ...	Contents of the second file are 0x85, 0x85, ...

(file continues)

```
./lcnl_encoder f000 u8be f001 f002
```

“Score”	Description
0x02,	Tool is 'lcnl_encoder'.
0x01,	FILE; push file name to argument list.
0x00, 0x75, 0x38, 0x62, 0x65, 0x00,	ARGUMENT; push string 'u8be' to the argument list.
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0x01,	FILE; push file name to argument list.
0x6e,	Unknown action; end of argument list construction.
0x02, 0x00, 0x00, 0x00, 0x00, 0x02, ..., 0x01, 0x00,	Contents of the first file are 0x00, 0x00, 0x02, ..., 0x01.
0x05, 0x85, 0x85, ...	Contents of the second file are 0x85, 0x85, ...

(file continues)

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0x02, 0x00, 0x00, 0x00, 0x00, 0x02, ..., 0x01, 0x00,	Contents of the first file are 0x00, 0x00, 0x02, ..., 0x01.
0x05, 0x85, 0x85, ...	Contents of the second file are 0x85, 0x85, ...

**Fuzzer learned how to use all command-line tools
...and even produced valid compressed files!**

Conclusions

Fuzzing was employed during the cross-validation of CCSDS 123.0-B-2:

- four teams produced independent implementations,
- test vectors were produced very efficiently, and
- **use fuzzing!**

...what about hardware designs?

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